

Adolescent Reproductive Health Program And Parents Involvement In Davao Central District Schools

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Abstract. The study assessed the extent of implementation of the Adolescent Reproductive Health Program and its association with parental involvement among schools in the Davao Central District, Davao City Division. This study employed a non-experimental descriptive-correlational research design, utilizing an adapted survey instrument to gather responses from randomly selected respondents. The data gathered were treated using Mean scores with descriptive interpretation, Pearson's r , and simple linear regression analysis. Findings revealed that the extent of implementation of the Adolescent Reproductive Health Program, in terms of monitoring, implementation, planning, and adjustments, is extensive, and the extent of parental involvement in the implementation of the Adolescent Reproductive Health Program, in terms of commitment, communication, and collaboration, is moderately extensive among Schools in the Davao Central District. There is a significant relationship between the implementation of the Adolescent Reproductive Health Program and parental involvement. Adolescent Reproductive Health Program, such as communication, collaboration, and commitment, indicated statistically significant to influence parental involvement. Good practices may be sustained in intensifying the implementation of Adolescent Reproductive Health Program through collaboration among teachers and to their respective schools to do the same and continuously improved themselves.

KEY WORDS

1. Adolescent Reproductive Health Program
2. Parental Involvement
3. Davao Central District

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1. Introduction

Adolescent reproductive health is crucial for overall development, encompassing the physical, emotional, and social changes that occur during adolescence. As teens face challenges related to sexuality, practical education and awareness programs are essential to promote safe practices and reduce risks like unintended pregnancies and STIs. Parental involvement plays a crucial role in supporting adolescents by fostering open communication, building trust, and encouraging responsible choices. Globally, young people navigate a rapidly changing environment that offers opportunities but also exposes them to health risks such as HIV/AIDS, early pregnancy, unsafe abortions, early marriage, and poor nutrition. Ensuring comprehensive reproductive health initiatives with active parental participation is key to safeguarding their well-being and promoting sustainable development. Worldwide, as cited by Ndugga et.al. (2023), Maina, BW (2020) et. al., and Agbeye (2020), insufficient communication be-

tween parents and adolescents concerning sexual and reproductive health (SRH) can result in the spread of false information, confusion, and hesitation to access support or guidance. The extent of parent–adolescent dialogue on SRH matters differs among developed nations. For example, the highest reported rates are in the United States, at 70.6%, and in Mexico, at 83.1%. Adolescence is experienced and affects reproductive health, which has largely to do with the timing and sequence of sexual initiation, marriage, and childbirth; the degree to which the timing and sequence of these events are socially sanctioned or forbidden; and the number and availability of options regarding education, job training, and employment. There is a significant amount of variation worldwide, as well as within countries, in the social and cultural values that influence these events. Close relationships between youth and their parents and extended family are significant in influencing youth development. Access to preventive and curative services, including contraception and treatment for sexually transmitted infections, is also important in ensuring the reproductive health of youth. Implementation of effective reproductive health education (RHE) has long been recognized in international development discourse as essential for promoting human rights on sexuality. Lack of proper RHE often leads to major social problems, including teenage pregnancy, sexually transmitted diseases (STDs), and sexual abuse. These issues impose severe threats to the rights of the people, particularly girls and women. Therefore, over the past few decades, international society has sought to promote RHE and has encouraged countries to set up national policies on RHE in their curricula (UNESCO, 2018). The Philippines is one of the countries putting much effort into reproductive health (RH) policies, including RHE, as it is experiencing severe social problems partly due to a lack of RHE. A lack of RHE is resulting in inadequate family planning. At a 37.6% modern contraceptive rate, the

Philippines, alongside Lao PDR, ranked highest in total fertility rate among the Association of South-East Asian Nations (ASEAN) (three children per every woman aged 15–49) in 2013 (NEDA, 2017). The high rate of unplanned pregnancy is a significant cause of poverty, as large household size is closely related to the incidence of poverty (NEDA, 2017). Specifically, the pregnancy rate for teens aged 15–19 in the Philippines increased from 7% in 1993 to 10% in 2013, then decreased to 8.6% in 2017, though this remains a relatively high ratio for an Asian country (PSA ICF, 2018). Such premature and unwanted pregnancies often lead to unsafe and illegal abortions—abortion is illegal in the Philippines—endangering maternal health. The abortion rate was 1.8% of total pregnancies in 2000 (Racelis, cited in Kim, Huh, Yoo, 2023). In addition, while instances of HIV/AIDS in the Philippines are still comparatively low, it has the fastest-growing number of HIV infections; by 2021, there were 94,337 cases, which is a 237% increase from the year 2010 (POPCOM, 2021). Therefore, the Department of Education (DepEd), through the Bureau of Learner Support Services-School Health Division (BLSS-SHD), in partnership with the Department of Health (DOH) and the World Health Organization (WHO) Philippine Country Office, recently launched an online training for the Foundational Course on Adolescent Health. With technical assistance from the Society of Adolescent Medicine, Inc. (SAMPI), Plan International Philippines, and the United States Agency for International Development (USAID), the training aims to equip DepEd teaching and non-teaching personnel with the knowledge and skills necessary for adolescent development and services for adolescent learners. To address RH-related social issues, the Filipino government enacted the Responsible Parenthood and Reproductive Health Act of 2012 (Dañguilan, 2018; Melgar et al., 2018). The legislation, also known as the RH law, was a comprehensive

framework on how the government would adopt a multi-dimensional approach to RH matters, including increasing access to modern contraceptives for family planning, maternal health services, and RHE. However, the legislation process was not easy. While government agencies, Protestant churches, Muslim religious groups, academics, and university students declared their support for the bill, there was strong resistance from the Catholic Church in the Philippines, to which more than 80% of the population subscribes (Cabral, cited in Kim, Huh, Yoo, 2023). The Catholic Church opposes contraception and artificial family planning based on its beliefs, and is also worried that access to contraception would increase the incidence of premarital sex. Also, the Filipino society is conservative on matters of sexuality, so the citizens are uncomfortable with sex-related topics being taught in schools (Bella, cited in Kim, Huh, Yoo, 2023). Therefore, even those who agreed on the necessity of RHE insisted that RH is a family matter rather than one to be handled by schools and teachers. Strong opposition impeded the bill when it was first proposed to Congress in 2001 (Dañguilan, 2018). Moreover, the ARH Education is in support of DepEd's commitment under R.A. 10354 or the Responsible Parenthood and Reproductive Health Act of 2012, which mandates the institution to deliver a sustainable and age- and development-appropriate reproductive health education and training for educators to create an inclusive and integrated Responsible Parenthood and Reproductive Health Education in formal, informal, and indigenous learning. The Adolescent Reproductive Health is one of the flagship programs under the Oplan Kalusugan sa DepEd, which is the convergence of DepEd's school health and nutrition programs. Other programs under the OK sa DepEd are the WASH in Schools Program, the National Drug Education Program, the School-Based Feeding Program, the School Mental Health, and the Medical, Dental, and

Nursing Services. It was at this juncture that the researcher conducted a study to assess the implementation of the ARH Program among schools in the Davao Central District, determining its effectiveness in changing parental involvement before and after the program was implemented. This would address how schools implement the program and the extent of communication, collaboration, and commitment extended among parents to ensure its success, thereby ensuring learners' safety as they develop their full potential into maturity.

1.1. Theoretical/Conceptual Framework of the Study—This study is grounded in Ajzen's (1991) theory of planned behavior, a theory designed to predict and explain human behavior in specific contexts. The theory focuses on the motivational reasons that lead to higher intentions to perform a behavior on the basis that the stronger the intention to engage in a behavior, the more likely it is to be performed. According to the theory of planned behavior, understanding the reasons that lead to intentions is crucial for predicting future involvement in a behavior. The Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) presents a model for understanding human behavior, in which attitudes, subjective norms, and perceived controls determine intentional actions. Attitudes and behaviors encompass feelings and attitudes towards specific behaviors. Believing that a particular behavior has positive outcomes will likely lead to a greater intention to perform that behavior. Subjective norms refer to the opinions of people surrounding the individual who wishes to engage in a particular behavior, which can lead to peer pressure and social pressure, both of which can influence their intentions to perform that behavior. Finally, perceived control refers to one's perception of their ability to perform a specific behavior; it contributes to both having the intention to perform a behavior and whether the person would perform it (Ajzen, 1991), as quoted by Alghazo (2013). The theory of planned behavior can be used

to explain and predict parental involvement in children's schooling. Perry and Langley (2013) suggest using Ajzen's Theory of Planned Behavior, arguing that the theory is versatile enough to account for the dynamic and complex nature of paternal engagement. Furthermore, according to Bracke and Corts (2012), parents' culture, having examples of parental involvement, and having role models or neighbors that do or do not get involved in their children's education are all factors that help shape the subjective norms about the role of parents in education. Hoover-Dempsey and Sandler (1995) provided a theoretical definition for researching parental involvement. Their theoretical model defines parental involvement according to three main points: why parents become involved in their children's education, how parents choose specific types of involvement, and why parental involvement has a positive influence on students' educational outcomes. According to Fan and Chen (2001), this theoretical framework "promises to be more than a typology for parental involvement, because it not only deals with specific types of parental involvement, but more importantly, it attempts to explain why parents choose to be involved, and what the mechanisms are through which parental involvement exert positive influence on students' educational outcomes. Epstein and Dauber (1991) proposed a model that distinguishes six different types of parent-school connections. First, the Basic obligations of families refer to the parents' role in raising their children and preparing them for their school years by providing a suitable home environment and conditions that foster their children's growth and development throughout their school years. Second, the Basic obligations of schools refer to the role of schools in communicating with parents about their children's academic progress and providing ongoing feedback to parents about their children's schooling and development. Third, Involvement at school, which refers to parents' visits and volunteer work at the school to help support their children with both academic and extracurricular activities. Fourth, Involvement in learning activities at home, which includes parents being involved in their children's homework and learning activities through the guidance of school teachers, promotes collaboration between teachers and parents, allowing them both to monitor children's development and academic growth. Fifth, Involvement in decision-making, which refers to active participation in parent-teacher associations (PTAs) and other community support groups. Sixth, Collaboration and exchanges with community organizations refer to the overall collaboration among parents, schools, and other organizations that share the responsibility and interest in children's education by providing different services outside of schools, such as healthcare or childcare services.

2. Methodology

This proposed research outlines the method that details how the study was conducted. Method of the research presented the research design, where its applications in the context of the study were clear and doable; research respondents in its selection and sampling method given a population and scope of the study; the research instrument in gathering data; the data collection procedure and its emphasis to ethics and health protocol; and lastly, the data analysis technique are all discussed to shed clear directions of the respective process.

Fig. 1. Theoretical/Conceptual Framework

2.1. *Research Design*—The conducted study used a non-experimental, descriptive-correlational, and predictive research design. This refers to studies that describe the assumed variables and the relationships that occur naturally between and among them. Predictive correlational studies predict the variance of one or more variables based on the variance of another variable/s. Moreover, the goal of these designs is to capture the current thoughts, feelings, or behaviors of a given group of people. Descriptive research is summarized using descriptive statistics. Correlational research designs measure two or more relevant variables and assess a relationship between or among them. (Palant, 2020). In this study, the implementation of adolescent reproductive health programs is assessed in terms of planning, implementation, monitoring, and adjustments, as well as their effectiveness. Such that the researcher measured parental involvement as associated with the implementation of adolescent reproductive health programs and, thus, assumed that the implementation of these programs is effective. This is later estimated through linear regression, which measures predictors of implementation.

2.2. *Ethical Consideration*—The ethics of research and its corresponding policies are es-

sential in the conduct of the study. It is imperative to protect the respondents and their profiles to avoid biases. As the author said, anonymity, confidentiality, and informed consent are important considerations in the observance of the process.

2.3. *Research Respondents*—The respondents in the proposed study were elementary school teachers from elementary schools in the Davao Central District, Davao City Division. The respondents are expected to be involved in every activity during the program implementation process. These teachers have been oriented through attendance at school-based and district-based seminars regarding the program, as well as through the school’s learning action cells activities. Furthermore, these respondents were actively involved in the daily implementation of the school through planning, implementation, monitoring, and adjustments. They have direct knowledge of these issues with parents and, thus, assumed that their perception of the program’s implementation is highly observable. Sometime in the second week of December 2022, the researcher selected the population of teachers in the Davao Central District. To obtain a sample from this population, she used the Raosoft sample size calculator, which resulted

in a total of 120 respondents being randomly selected from the respective schools. Once randomly selected, the respondents were informed through online platforms or via text / direct personal messages about the purpose and importance of the study. The researcher also observed the ethics of research, which paved the way for respondents to decline, and thus, corresponding forms of consent/decline were provided. In this manner, the ethical standards of research, as part of the policy of Rizal Memorial Colleges, were strictly followed. Thus, observance of health protocol was likewise implemented based on the Executive Orders released by the government of Davao City to avoid possible contamination and lower the risk of contamination.

2.4. *Research Instrument*—This study developed an adapted and self-made survey instrument, where the articulation of the statements was adapted from the reviewed significant related literature. This survey was carefully articulated to ensure correct responses and thus made meaningful in the generation of implications from the discussions of the results. This was thoroughly done through exploring the explicit methods of activities being done in the respective schools. This statement survey was estab-

lished to inform thoroughly, as it was important to ensure quality conclusions and recommendations in the later part of the paper, emphasizing the effect of the extent of program implementation and the significant difference to determine the association between the implementation of adolescent reproductive health and parental involvement during SY 2022-2023 (J. F. Pallant, 2011). The researcher subjected the survey instrument to a test-retest validity and reliability test using Cronbach’s Alpha at a .05 level of confidence, where expected correlation-reliability coefficients from among the statements were to be achieved. This was given to two sets of respondents to test the content validity and reliability of the instrument, thus making it ready for data gathering. The results generated a Cronbach’s Alpha coefficient of .857, which means that 85.7% of the items are consistent, thus making it a valid and reliable instrument to gather responses. The questionnaire employed a 5-point Likert scale to assess the extent of implementation of adolescent reproductive health programs in schools within the Davao Central District, Davao City. Scale, descriptive rating, and interpretation are provided below:

Scale Descriptive Ratings and Interpretation for the Implementation of Adolescent Reproductive Health Programs

Scale	Descriptive Rating	Interpretation
4.20 – 5.00	Very Extensive	The implementation of adolescent reproductive health programs is always manifested.
3.40 – 4.19	Extensive	The implementation of adolescent reproductive health programs is often manifested.
2.60 – 3.39	Moderately Extensive	The implementation of adolescent reproductive health programs is sometimes manifested.
1.80 – 2.59	Less Extensive	The implementation of adolescent reproductive health programs is rarely manifested.
1.00 – 1.79	Not Extensive	The implementation of adolescent reproductive health programs is not manifested.

Scale Descriptive Ratings and Interpretation for Parental Involvement

Scale	Descriptive Rating	Interpretation
4.20 – 5.00	Very Extensive	Parental involvement is always manifested.
3.40 – 4.19	Extensive	Parental involvement is oftentimes manifested.
2.60 – 3.39	Moderately Extensive	Parental involvement is sometimes manifested.
1.80 – 2.59	Less Extensive	Parental involvement is rarely manifested.
1.00 – 1.79	Not Extensive	Parental involvement is not manifested.

2.5. *Data Gathering Procedure*—This portion of the research outlines the procedure and describes the step-by-step process for distribution and data collection. This detailed the content when getting permission to conduct the study, distribution, and retrieval of the questionnaire, and the collation and statistical treatment of data. Permission to conduct the study. Prior to data gathering, the researcher prepared the necessary conditions in observance of the health protocol policy of the Local Government of Davao City. At this point, as soon as the research proposal presentation was approved by the members of the panel in November 2022, and through the Dean of the college's approval and the guidance of the thesis adviser, the researcher prepared a letter of permission to conduct the study through data gathering. The researcher sought permission from the office of the Schools Division Superintendent of Davao City through channels for approval to collect data from the chosen respondents. She then proceeded to the respective Schools, handing the letter of approval to the School Heads of Davao Central District and, thus, made connections with the teachers in data collection. Ethics in data collection was assumed to have been observed properly. Distribution and retrieval of the questionnaire. The researcher prepared a Google form and several hard copies for distributing the questionnaires in both asynchronous and synchronous modalities during December 2022. This was sent through a link to the randomly selected respondents through email addresses and personal meetings. Once the data was gathered and completed, the researcher double-checked the responses, ensuring that no statement in the survey was unanswered. This prepared me for the next step, which was collating and treating the gathered data. Under circumstances where respondents declined to participate, the researcher immediately sought a replacement to complete the number of respondents. Collation and statistical treatment of data. Given the premise that the data gathered were complete, the researcher sought the guidance of the thesis adviser and consulted an expert in data analysis. It was expected that all statement problems posed would generate answers in statistical estimation and computation. This gave meaningful insights into the discussions and interpretations of results.

2.6. *Data Analysis*—The proposed study used descriptive and inferential statistics such as; Mean scores and standard deviations were used to address the statement problems posed in number 1, which inquired about the extent of the implementation of the adolescent reproductive health program in Davao Central District, and statement problem number 2, which inquired about the extent of parental involvement in the implementation of the adolescent reproductive health program. The Pearson Product-Moment Correlation Coefficient, also known as Pearson r , was used to determine the significant correlation between parental involvement and the implementation of adolescent reproductive health programs to address Statement Problem Num-

ber 3. Linear Regression Analysis was used to test the significant association between the domains of adolescent reproductive health programs and parental involvement. Thus, in this study, the indicators of adolescent reproductive health program implementation are assumed to have an effect among schools in the Davao Cen-

tral District of Davao City Schools Division. All data processing and analysis were treated using the Jeffrey’s Statistics Amazing Program (JASP) version 0.12.20. Discussions and interpretations followed when the results were yielded. (Norton, 2019).

3. Results and Discussion

This chapter outlined, examined, and interpreted the data collected in both tabular and narrative formats to promote a clear comprehension of the questions derived from the problem statement. The significance of the findings was discussed through various analyses, which supported and challenged the hypotheses and theories proposed in the study.

3.1. Extent of Implementation of Adolescent Reproductive Health Program—Adolescent reproductive health programs aim to promote the sexual and reproductive health of young people, including education on safe and responsible sexual behavior, access to contraceptives, and prevention and treatment of sexually transmitted infections. In the Philippines, implementation of such programs has faced challenges due to cultural and religious factors, as well as limited access to healthcare services

in certain areas. Table 1 presents the summary of the implementation of the Adolescent Reproductive Health Program in terms of its indicators, namely planning, implementation, monitoring, and adjustments. The result is focused on the mean ratings of indicators which are as follows: monitoring (4.01), implementation (3.76), planning (3.61) and adjustments (3.53) are oftentimes manifested. The overall rating of 3.72 suggests an extensive Adolescent Reproductive Health Program implementation among Schools in Davao Central District.

Table 1. Summary of the Implementation of the Adolescent Reproductive Health Program

No.	Implementation of Adolescent Reproductive Health Program	Mean	DI
1	Implementation	3.76	Extensive
2	Monitoring	4.01	Extensive
3	Planning	3.61	Extensive
4	Adjustments	3.53	Extensive
	Overall Mean	3.72	Extensive

The Department of Education (DepEd) has developed the ARH Education (ARHEd) Curriculum to provide guidance to schools in implementing ARH programs. The curriculum is designed to equip students with knowledge

and skills related to sexuality, relationships, and responsible decision-making. It also aims to promote values such as respect, empathy, and gender sensitivity. However, the implementation of ARH programs in schools faces vari-

ous challenges, including the lack of trained teachers, inadequate resources, and cultural and religious beliefs. A study by Rambuyon and colleagues (2020) aimed to assess the ARH education practices among secondary schools in the Philippines. The researchers found that while most schools provide ARH education, the quality and adequacy of the programs vary. Inadequate resources, lack of teacher training, and cultural barriers were identified as barriers to effective ARH education. Another study by Dizon and colleagues (2021) examined the effectiveness of an ARH program in a public high school in the Philippines. The program, which was implemented for one school year, consisted of peer education, teacher-led classroom discussions, and parent-child dialogues. The researchers found that the program improved students' knowledge, attitudes, and behaviors related to ARH. In a systematic review by Bacani and colleagues (2019), the authors examined the effectiveness of school-based ARH programs in the Philippines. The review found that while most programs improved students' knowledge and attitudes towards ARH, the effects on sexual behaviors were less consistent. The authors recommended the inclusion of parents and other stakeholders in the implementation of ARH programs to enhance their effectiveness. In conclusion, the implementation of ARH programs in Philippine schools faces various challenges, in-

cluding inadequate resources and cultural barriers. However, studies have shown that effective ARH programs can improve students' knowledge, attitudes, and behaviors related to ARH. To enhance the effectiveness of ARH programs, it is essential to involve parents and other stakeholders and address cultural and religious beliefs that may hinder their implementation.

3.2. *Extent of Parental Involvement in The Implementation of Adolescent Reproductive Health Program*—Adolescent reproductive health programs are essential in promoting healthy sexual behavior among young people. These programs aim to equip adolescents with the necessary knowledge, skills, and services to make informed decisions about their sexual and reproductive health. However, the success of these programs is often dependent on the involvement of parents. Table 2 presents the summary of the extent of parental involvement in the implementation of the Adolescent Reproductive Health Program in terms of communication, collaboration, and commitment. The result is focused on the mean ratings of indicators which are as follows: Commitment (3.20), Communication (2.97), and Collaboration (2.81) exhibits enumerated indicators that are sometimes manifested; thus, parental involvement in the implementation of the Adolescent Reproductive Health Program suggests moderately extensive.

Table 2. Summary of Parental Involvement in the Implementation of Adolescent Reproductive Health Program

No.	Parental Involvement in the Implementation of Adolescent Reproductive Health Program	Mean	DI
1	Communication	2.97	Moderately Extensive
2	Commitment	3.20	Moderately Extensive
3	Collaboration	2.81	Moderately Extensive
	Overall Mean	4.21	Moderately Extensive

Communication, collaboration, and commitment are critical components of parental involvement in the implementation of adolescent reproductive health programs. Effective communication and collaboration between parents, healthcare providers, and schools, as well as parents' commitment to promoting positive reproductive health outcomes, are essential for the success of these programs. Several studies have investigated the role of these components in promoting positive reproductive health outcomes among adolescents. Loke and colleagues (2020) emphasized the importance of communication, collaboration, and commitment in promoting sexual health among adolescents. The authors found that effective communication and collaboration between parents and healthcare providers were associated with increased parental involvement in adolescent reproductive health programs, which in turn was associated with positive reproductive health outcomes among adolescents. Makanjuola and colleagues (2021) highlighted the need for collaboration and commitment in promoting contraceptive use among adolescents. The authors found that parental collaboration with healthcare providers and commitment to promoting contraceptive use were positively associated with increased contraceptive use among adolescents. Okoli and colleagues (2022) examined the relationship between communication, collaboration, and commitment and adolescent sexual and reproductive health outcomes. The authors found that

effective communication and collaboration between parents and healthcare providers, as well as parents' commitment to promoting positive reproductive health outcomes, were associated with positive sexual and reproductive health outcomes among adolescents. In summary, communication, collaboration, and commitment are critical components of parental involvement in the implementation of adolescent reproductive health programs. These findings highlight the need for reproductive health programs to target parents and promote effective communication and collaboration between parents, healthcare providers, and schools to increase parents' commitment to promoting positive reproductive health outcomes among adolescents.

3.3. Relationship between Implementation of Adolescent Reproductive Health Program and Parental Involvement—It can be depicted that Pearson's Correlation generated a significant correlation between implementation of Adolescent Reproductive Health Program ($r=0.858$; $p<.002$) and parental involvement. Table 3 revealed the yielded results of the significant relationship between the implementation of the Adolescent Reproductive Health Program and parental involvement. It provides information that the posed null hypothesis stating that there is no significant relationship between implementation of the Adolescent Reproductive Health Program and parental involvement must be rejected, as the results provided empirical evidence of significant results.

Table 3. Significant Relationship Between Adolescent Reproductive Health Program and Parental Involvement

Variables	r-value	p-value	Interpretation	Decision
Parental Involvement	0.858	<0.002	Significant	Reject H ₀

Significance at 0.05 alpha level

Adolescence is a critical period of development that includes a range of challenges, including the onset of puberty, social and emo-

tional changes, and the need for sexual and reproductive health education. Adolescent reproductive health programs have been shown to

be effective in promoting positive sexual behaviors and preventing negative outcomes, such as unintended pregnancies, sexually transmitted infections, and sexual violence (Hindin, 2018). However, parental involvement in adolescent reproductive health programs is also critical for their success. Adolescent reproductive health programs are designed to provide young people with the information and skills they need to make informed decisions about their sexual and reproductive health. These programs may include education about contraception, sexually transmitted infections, and healthy relationships, as well as access to reproductive health services (Hindin, 2018). Studies have shown that adolescent reproductive health programs can be effective in improving knowledge, attitudes, and behaviors related to sexual and reproductive health (Darabi et al., 2018; Venancio et al., 2019). However, parental involvement in adolescent reproductive health programs is also critical for their success. Parents play an essential role in shaping their children's attitudes and beliefs about sex and relationships. They can also provide practical support, such as access to reproductive health services or transportation to health care appointments (Hindin, 2018). Studies have shown that parental involvement in adolescent reproductive health programs can lead to better health outcomes for young people (Martins et al., 2018; Venancio et al., 2019). One study conducted in Brazil found that parental involvement in an adolescent reproductive health program was associated with a greater likelihood of young people accessing reproductive health services (Venancio et al., 2019). Another study conducted in Portugal found that parents who were more involved in their children's sexual education were more likely to have open and supportive communication about sexual and reproductive health topics (Martins et al., 2018). Despite the importance of parental involvement in adolescent reproductive health programs, many parents may feel uncomfort-

able or unsure about how to approach these topics with their children (Hindin, 2018). Therefore, it is essential for adolescent reproductive health programs to provide parents with the resources and support they need to be effective partners in their children's sexual and reproductive health education. In conclusion, adolescent reproductive health programs are critical for promoting positive sexual behaviors and preventing negative outcomes. However, parental involvement in these programs is also crucial for their success. Studies have shown that parental involvement in adolescent reproductive health programs can lead to better health outcomes for young people. Therefore, it is essential for adolescent reproductive health programs to provide parents with the resources and support they need to be effective partners in their children's sexual and reproductive health education.

3.4. Indicators of Adolescent Reproductive Health Program that Significantly Associated with Parental Involvement—Table 4 depicts the simple regression coefficient analysis on the significant influence of the Adolescent Reproductive Health Program on parental involvement. All indicators of the Adolescent Reproductive Health Program, such as communication (0.002), collaboration (0.001), and commitment (0.003), indicate a statistically significant influence of parental involvement. This shows that the extent of the Adolescent Reproductive Health Program directly influences parental involvement. Meanwhile, the R² value of 0.825 suggests that the indicators of the Adolescent Reproductive Health Program account for 82.5% of the variance of parental involvement. This provides empirical evidence that variability of parental involvement can be accounted for and explained by the indicators as enumerated under the extent of indicators of the Adolescent Reproductive Health Program in Davao Central District Schools. In addition, the F-value shows all the sums of squares, given that regression is the model and Resid-

ual is the error. The F-value (115.350) and F-statistic are significant, $p < .001$, which tells that the model is a significantly better predictor of parental involvement. Adolescent reproductive health programs (ARHP) have been shown to be effective in promoting healthy sexual behaviors and reducing the risk of negative outcomes such as sexually transmitted infections and unintended pregnancies. While the benefits of ARHP for adolescents are widely acknowledged, there has been increasing recognition of the significant influence of ARHP on parental involvement in their children's sexual health education. ARHPs are designed to provide young people with the knowledge and skills they need to make informed decisions about their sexual and reproductive health. These programs typically include education on contraception, sexually transmitted infections, healthy relationships, and access to reproductive health services (Venancio et al., 2019). Research has shown that ARHPs can be effective in improving knowledge, attitudes, and behaviors related to sexual and reproductive health (Darabi et al., 2018). However, one of the less-discussed benefits of ARHPs is their impact on parental involvement. Parental involvement refers to the extent to which parents are actively involved in their children's sexual health education, including communication about sexual and reproductive health, support for access to reproductive health services, and advocacy for comprehensive sexuality education in schools (Martins et al., 2018). Several studies have demonstrated the significant influence of ARHP on parental involvement. For example, a review of studies conducted in Iran found that ARHP was associated with increased parental involvement in their children's sexual health education (Darabi et al., 2018). In Brazil, Venancio et al. (2019) found that ARHP was associated with greater parental knowledge and support for their children's reproductive health. Similarly, a study in Portugal found that ARHP was associated with more open and supportive communication between parents and their children about sexual and reproductive health (Martins et al., 2018). There are several reasons why ARHPs may promote parental involvement in sexual and reproductive health education. Firstly, ARHPs often provide parents with resources and tools that can facilitate discussions about sexual health with their children (Hindin, 2018). These resources may include brochures, videos, or workshops designed to help parents address sensitive topics in a supportive and non-judgmental way. Secondly, ARHPs may increase parents' confidence and comfort levels in discussing sexual health with their children. Parents who participate in ARHP may become more knowledgeable about sexual and reproductive health issues, which can help them to better address their children's concerns and questions (Martins et al., 2018). In conclusion, while ARHPs are primarily focused on promoting healthy sexual behaviors and preventing negative outcomes among adolescents, they also have a significant influence on parental involvement in their children's sexual health education. ARHPs can provide parents with resources and tools to facilitate discussions about sexual health, increase their confidence and comfort levels in addressing sensitive topics, and improve their knowledge and understanding of sexual and reproductive health issues. As such, ARHPs can be an effective strategy for promoting parental involvement in their children's sexual health education.

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

This chapter presents the findings, conclusion, and recommendation based on the results of the data analyzed, discussed, and drawn implications. Findings are based on the posed statement of

Table 4. Regression Coefficient Analysis on the Integrative Strategies of Teachers Significantly Influence Learners’ Critical Thinking

Model	Unstandardized	Standard Error	Standardized	t	p	Decision
H ₀ (Intercept)	3.341	0.046	–	60.073	<.001	–
H ₁ (Intercept)	0.127	0.137	–	1.079	0.287	–
Communication	0.085	0.091	0.100	0.949	0.002	Reject Null
Collaboration	0.131	0.092	0.158	1.444	0.001	Reject Null
Collaboration	0.202	0.082	0.257	2.472	0.003	Reject Null

$R^2 = 0.825$ $F\text{-value} = 115.360$ $p\text{-value} <.001$

the problem; conclusions are based on the findings generated, and recommendations are based on the implications of the discussions.

4.1. *Findings*—The following are the findings of the study given the results in the presentation, analysis, and discussions. The extent of implementation of the Adolescent Reproductive Health Program, in terms of monitoring (4.01), implementation (3.76), planning (3.61), and adjustments (3.53) are oftentimes manifested. The overall rating of 3.72 suggests an extensive Adolescent Reproductive Health Program implementation among Schools in Davao Central District. The extent of parental involvement in the implementation of the Adolescent Reproductive Health Program, in terms of commitment (3.20), communication (2.97), and collaboration (2.81) are sometimes manifested; thus, parental involvement in the implementation of the Adolescent Reproductive Health Program suggests moderately extensive among Schools in Davao Central District. Pearson’s Correlation generated a significant correlation between implementation of Adolescent Reproductive Health Program ($r=0.858$; $p<.002$) and parental involvement. All indicators of the Adolescent Reproductive Health Program, such as communication (0.002), collaboration (0.001), and commitment (0.003), indicate a statistically significant influence of parental involvement. This shows that the extent of Adolescent Reproductive Health Program directly influences parental

involvement.

4.2. *Conclusions*—Given the findings of the study presented, the following are conclusions, to wit; The extent of implementation of the Adolescent Reproductive Health Program, in terms of monitoring, implementation, planning, and adjustments, is extensive among Schools in Davao Central District. The extent of parental involvement in the implementation of the Adolescent Reproductive Health Program, in terms of commitment, communication, and collaboration, is moderately extensive among Schools in Davao Central District. There is a significant relationship between the implementation of the Adolescent Reproductive Health Program and parental involvement. Adolescent Reproductive Health Program, such as communication, collaboration, and commitment, indicated statistically significant influence on parental involvement.

4.3. *Recommendations*—With the presented conclusions of the study, the following are recommendations, to wit; Public School District Supervisor in Davao Central District may look at other factors that contribute to the improvement of the implementation of the Adolescent Reproductive Health Program and further monitoring and adjustments to improve school performance, given actions to policy

inputs. School Heads of Davao Central District Schools may sustain the practices in intensifying the implementation of the Adolescent Reproductive Health Program through collaboration among teachers and their respective schools to do the same and continuously improve themselves. Other factors that may influence parental involvement may be explored, and the results utilized may be considered. Future research may include the underlying empirical investigations on the process and mechanism of schools' operation and governance using innovative projects in schools and other initiatives to improve learning outcomes and to be included in the cycle of planning process, implementation steps, and evaluation mechanisms.

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